

MEASURING THE SIMILARITY OF GRAPHICAL OBJECTS, GROUPS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Establishing a new palaeographic methodology

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Summary

The author summarises a possible methodology for computer-based palaeographic research, which has been outlined in a previous article, but which has not yet had a very significant history. He takes stock of the solutions and possibilities published in the small number of publications available on the subject, qualifies the approaches on the basis of his own experimental experience, and then suggests a metric for expressing the similarity of graphic objects and a possible treatment of group similarity.

The method consists of training an AI classifier to recognise patterns of a selected reference group (reference language, context) and then trying to recognise another group in its context. The result is a cross-similarity matrix, as an estimate of the degree of similarity, which will be the basis for further processing - e.g. to calculate the degree of group similarity and plausibility.

The subject of palaeographic research is mostly excavated material from a single group, which is thus unsuitable for training an artificial intelligence classifier. This problem is solved by generating a training set obtained by random but controlled distortion of the original corpus.

In teaching, it makes the mappings embedded in the AI more human-controlled by making comparisons in a human-consistent, exactly computable space of aspects, where the AI decides their object-specific importance.

Keywords

Paleography, similarity metrics, measurement of graphical features, contextual similarity, machine learning, supervised training, image processing, artificial intelligence classifier, SVM, multilayer neural network.

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Foreword

If, for example, a stack of seal impressions is found on an archaeological site and there is reason to believe that they were not next to each other by chance, they were probably part of a trade relationship.

Given an already known set of signals, a group similarity measure can be searched for and perhaps given, which can be used to determine the probable direction of a trade relationship, e.g. whether group B or C is the more likely, closer relationship to group A (reference, context). Using this technique, - the probable relatedness of the graphical group under consideration (A) to groups B, C and others can be explored by binary comparisons.

For this procedure to work, - on the one hand, the similarity measure of individual graphical objects must be metricated, - on the other hand, a similarity measure between groups must be derived from the mutual similarity measures of the group objects.

1. Introduction

The similarity of two graphical objects can also be metricized by comparing several invariant geometric properties and then projecting the degree of similarity of the properties into the range 0...1 by a multivariate function, for example, giving a similarity measure, accepting it as an estimator of a similarity probability. This aggregating unknown function can be "discovered" by a machine learning classifier, e.g. a suitably chosen neural network.

Structure of the article:

In section 2, we briefly review the solutions used in image processing for describing the characteristics of graphical objects and for metrics of similarity, their advantages and disadvantages. In Sections 2.4 and 2.5 we evaluate three published paleographic solutions, and in Section 2.6 we reformulate the similarity function criteria and

propose a statistical classifier for estimating the aggregate similarity value. In section 3, based on our own experience and the method implemented, we propose similarity characteristic functions that have been found useful and applied. At the end of this section, we present the results of an application example, and in section 4 we discuss future possibilities.

2. Describing graphical objects, measuring similarity

2.1. Using classical orthogonal function resolutions

It seems obvious to compress graphical objects with the same angular position and scale using orthogonal functions (2D FFT, 2D DCT, etc.) and then express the similarity in transform space. However, there are several problems with these solutions:

- on the one hand, an acceptable description of the mostly linear graphical diagrams is associated with a high harmonic content,
- on the other hand, the more important problem is that the concepts of distance (and proximity) defined in transformational space are very different from the morphological but fundamentally very difficult to describe way of human vision and interpretation.

2.2. Using the classical similarity metrics

The most common similarity metrics are, e.g.:

- the normalised cross-correlation (NCC),
- the phase correlation,
- or the sum of the absolute value of the differences (SAD)

for line graphics give a monotonic dependence only for small deviations.

The situation can be improved by introducing a kernel function (e.g. Gaussian), which, by convolving the line images, makes the above similarity metrics tend to become more monotonic.

It is still true that the concepts of distance (and proximity) defined in this way are very different from the morphological but fundamentally very difficult to describe way of the human mechanism of vision and interpretation.

2.3. Use of geometry descriptors and contour inputs

Contour crawlers (e.g., bar codes) and Fourier descriptors are easy to compute and effective for describing certain graphical objects. However, many objects to be described in palaeography consist of several distinct parts that must be interpreted together, a situation that is difficult to handle with these methods.

2.4. Using solutions for character recognition

From the pre-decision threshold output of common OCR algorithms (pattern matching, feature point set matching, or e.g. convolutional neural networks (CNN), etc.) it is difficult to generate a monotonic, well-interpreted distance function, because:

- on the one hand, they are designed/trained for "too sharp" match detection,
- on the other hand, e.g. in the case of CNN, training requires a large teaching set, which is usually not available in paleographic applications.

Shruti Daggumati and co-author [1] propose the direct use of a multilayer deep learning convolutional neural network for symbol pair matching. They argue that different convolutional layers can be used to extract features according to different aspects and hence the size of the training sets can be reduced. This is true, but since many aspects cannot be described by a convolutional layer, handling sensitivity to many aspects is hopeless and only a refined design of the training set can help.

However, an important novelty is that, using the idea of F. Chollet [3], the size of the training set is enlarged by random transformations.

The previous authors [2] in their paper use a combination of CNN+SVM (Support Vector Machine), where the CNN layers form an output pattern according to the features, from which the SVM classifier generates a similarity score. The symbol sets of size $N \times M$ output a similarity matrix of size $N \times M$. The authors introduce two numbers for group similarity: - the average similarity, - and the selective similarity, the latter being the average of similarities

above 75%. Based on similarity numbers and time of origin data, a classification tree and a descent tree are created.

2.5. Speculative classification by geometrical characteristics

P. Z. Révész [4] describes graphical objects with a hypothetical resolution in terms of a set of geometric primitives. A similarity number is introduced by a weighted but arbitrary score of the matching by geometric primitives. Because of the difficulty in justifying the arbitrariness, the method cannot be considered to be of general use. The author also unleashed off this solution as a co-author of articles [1], [2].

2.6. Redefining the similarity criteria

As we have seen above, there are a number of problems with the methods discussed above.

2.6.1. Summary of the problems

- We have seen that the similarity functions generated per facet based on feature properties are either very speculative, - making the result very intuitive, or very difficult to control, or they are no visible because the criterion functions are "hidden" in the "soul" of the trained classifier.

- It also became clear that similarity should be considered from as many aspects as possible, because no single similarity criterion can be given that would work on any graphical set, or even slightly resemble human similarity concepts.

- Experience has shown that it is not possible to derive the unknown aggregating function problem from the feature similarity values produced for multiple facets, either for a simple linear or for a simple logarithmic combinator, where the aggregating function would give the aggregate similarity estimate from the facet similarity values.

To be able to calculate most of the image attributes, the image must be registered. We call image registration the process of finding the best overlapping geometric transformation between a reference image and the image to be matched [5]. For the moment, the way this is done is indifferent, for us it is the result of the transformation and the transformation matrix itself that is important. In the following, we consider the relation between the reference and the transformed image and the transformation matrix.

2.6.2. Limits of invariant characteristics

After applying the transformation matrix, only the limits of the scale and rotation invariances can be discussed

- The automaticity of image registration can make, for example, a small spot and a much larger circle into a coincident object. For this reason, a case-by-case scaling limit should be introduced.

- In the case of writing symbols, depending on the way of writing and reading, the symbols can be rotated +/-90 degrees, possibly mirrored, but it is very rare to find a symbol rotated 180 degrees but with the same meaning. In these cases, restrictions should also be introduced.

2.6.3. Ideally expected properties of characteristic functions

It is worth prescribing some criteria for the characteristic function describing the similarity by an aspect.

- Monotony. If it is not true for the aspect similarity function that the first derivative is always greater than zero, then the learning process of the aggregator may be prolonged or stopped.

- Although this is already included in the monotonicity condition, it is worth emphasizing that the characteristic function should not have long constant sections, since such sections can stop the training iteration.

- An aspect similarity function should be chosen that produces a response between 0 and 1, so that it can be interpreted as a probability estimator if it also satisfies the previous conditions.

2.6.4. Contextual training

If we train the aggregator classifier to recognize the symbol set A (reference, context) and then use the resulting classifier to evaluate the raw similarity matrices $A \sim B$ and $A \sim C$ (where 'B' and 'C' are each an additional symbol set), we obtain the estimate of the similarities $A \sim B$ and $A \sim C$ in the context of set A. That is, what the reader familiar with 'A' (contextually trained) recognizes as similar when seeing the symbol sets 'B' and 'C'.

2.7. Formulating group similarity

Let be a symbol set A with size N_a , and let be a classifier trained on A.

Then compare 'A' with the set 'B' of size N_b . The comparison gives the similarity matrix:

$$Sab \text{ of size } Na \times Nb.$$

Run through the matrix element by element from the direction of the smaller dimension (row by row or column by column) and leave the maximum element. The result is the Sab_{max} matrix.

Let there also be:

$$Nab_{min} = \min(Na, Nb); Nab_{max} = \max(Na, Nb).$$

Then we can define two useful values:

- Group similarity:

$$Sim_{ab} = \text{sum}(Sab_{max}) / Nab_{min};$$

so we take the average of the maximum similarity maxima that can actually be interpreted.

- Connection strength:

$$Cs_{ab} = Sim_{ab} * Nab_{min} / Nab_{max} = \text{sum}(Sab_{max}) / Nab_{max},$$

which expresses the empirical fact that the probable relationship between two symbol systems decreases with different sizes. This value can also be interpreted as a kind of confidence number, since the ratio:

$$Nab_{min} / Nab_{max} \text{ is the maximum of the conditional probability of group similarity.}$$

3. Main features of the developed method

3.1. Basic processing steps

For line symbol corpora, the following basic processing steps are performed:

- Set the same image size and line width.
- Image registration, transformation and production of the transformation matrix.

Figure 1: Finding the best fit without using a kernel function.

Figure 2: Finding the best fit using a kernel function

- Calculation of mutual similarity numbers per aspect for each element of the symbol set 'A' and 'B', resulting on a Lab raw similarity matrix of size $Na \times Nb \times Nf$, where Nf is the number of feature function values.

- When teaching the aggregating function (classifier), we train the degraded symbol set 'Ad' according to the Chollet idea mentioned above. The aim is to have approximately the same number of 'same' and 'not same' decision categories. As an example, the following image degradations can be proposed, with independent randomness and degree: x-y miss-scaling, clipping, allowable rotation, image completion, image detail omission. Since the resulting image degradations occur together, their magnitude should not be too large. Experience shows that 5% per aspect is a rough limit.

- After that, if the raw similarity matrix Lab is evaluated with the trained classifier, the classifier gives the similarity matrix Sab in the context of set A, and from this the matrix Sab_{max} can be formed.

- In the final step, the group similarity numbers can be computed with Sab_{max} .

Figure 3: Block diagram of the training process.

Figure 4: Block diagram of the similarity measurement process.

3.2. Concrete application example

3.2.1. Proposals and examples of similarity functions

After pre-processing and image registration, it was useful to introduce e.g. the following feature functions:

- $NCC(0,0)$ The value of the normalised cross correlation at the (0,0) offset point.
- X-Y miss-scaling. Example: $sc = \min(sx/sy, sy/sx)$. Where sx, sy are the scaling factor per coordinate direction derived from the transformation matrix.
- Similarity by degree of shear derived from the transformation matrix.
- Normalized SAD difference similarity computed from kernel function convolved images after transformation.
- Aggregate "image weight" by difference in similarity.

For example: let $v1 = \text{sum}(\text{sum}(\text{image}_1))$, $v2 = \text{sum}(\text{sum}(\text{image}_t))$;
 then $sv = \min(v1/v2, v2/v1)$.

- Similarity in the difference of the first-order polar moments.
- Similarity in the different proportions of the first-order moments x, y .
- The rotational similarity required to achieve congruence.

Many more aspects of similarity can be introduced. The big advantage of the method is its flexibility, since the way in which a feature function is included in the aggregation is decided during the learning process, so that the "intuitive" effect is reduced by having a sufficiently wide set of similarity feature functions.

3.2.2. Results of application examples

In our example, we compared 22-22 selected signals from Linear-A, 22 selected signals from Carian and 88 selected signals from Linear-B.

Figure 5: The maximum similarity matrix of a signal group of the Minoan Linear-A and Carian.

The original LA-Ca group similarity (in the LA context) was 0.53 and the connection strength was 0.53, as we selected just 22-22 very similar groups.

In the following example, we evaluated 88 signals of Linear-B using the SVM classifier trained in the context of Linear-A, which we used previously. (The multilayer neural network also gives the same result.)

Linear B Syllabary

	1000	1001	1002	1003	1004	1005	1006	1007
0	10000	10010	10020	10030	10040	10050		
1	10001	10011	10021	10031	10041	10051		
2	10002	10012	10022	10032	10042	10052		
3	10003	10013	10023	10033	10043	10053		
4	10004	10014	10024	10034	10044	10054		
5	10005	10015	10025	10035	10045	10055		
6	10006	10016	10026	10036	10046	10056		
7	10007	10017		10037	10047	10057		
8	10008	10018	10028	10038	10048	10058		
9	10009	10019	10029	10039	10049	10059		
A	1000A	1001A	1002A	1003A	1004A	1005A		
B	1000B	1001B	1002B		1004B	1005B		
C		1001C	1002C	1003C	1004C	1005C		
D	1000D	1001D	1002D	1003D	1004D	1005D		
E	1000E	1001E	1002E					
F	1000F	1001F	1002F	1003F				

Figure 6: Signal set of Linear-B .

The original LA~LB group similarity (in the LA context) was also found to be about 0.53, while the strength of connection was found to be 0.13, as we compared just 22-88 groups of very different sizes.

This surprising result, given the historical relationship, points out that arbitrarily picking out groups of signs from a larger set of signs can yield similarity between groups, but the arbitrary picking out of a different set of signs can result in a different confidence than expected. This result confirms the usefulness of the chosen group features, despite their simplicity.

Interestingly, the maximum similarity between the symbols of LA and Georgian Mkhedruli script is about 0.007 (~0.7%), reflecting the great distance between the two symbol systems.

4. Future challenges and opportunities

By organizing the manually executable Matlab (Image Processing Toolbox, Machine Learning Toolbox) functions and scripts into a Matlab (or Python) application that can also be processed in parallel, it is possible to process larger corpora.

By gaining access to palaeographically prepared archaeological corpus, their interconnection system could be explored more efficiently and systematically.

Motivated also by personal motivation, research on the Anatolian connections of the Minoan culture promises to be a very promising research, possibly with decisive new results, which will require finding the right working relationships.

Author's note:

I am sad to note that the first (2021) presentation of the method presented here ([6],[7]) was downloaded by some people, but used without any reference.

Literature

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